

A survey on Deep Learning-based Single Image Super-Resolution

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Abstract- Single Image Super-Resolution (SISR) is a fundamental task in computer vision with the aim to reconstruct high-resolution images from low-resolution counterparts. Deep learning has revolutionized SISR in recent years, enabling significant improvements in both reconstruction fidelity and perceptual quality. This survey provides a comprehensive review of deep learning-based SISR methods, categorizing them into four primary paradigms: convolutional neural networks, generative adversarial networks, transformers, and diffusion-based models. For each category, the architectural designs, their strengths and limitations are analyzed. The challenges being faced in this area and potential directions for future have been discussed. This survey aims to provide researchers with a unified understanding of the current state-of-the-art in deep-learning based SISR.

Keywords - Deep Learning, Single Image Super-Resolution, Generative Adversarial Networks, Convolutional Neural Networks, Transformer Networks, Diffusion Models, Survey

I. INTRODUCTION

Single Image Super-Resolution (SISR) addresses the problem of reconstructing a high-resolution (HR) image from a given low-resolution (LR) input. It is a critical task in computer vision and image processing, with wide-ranging applications including medical imaging [1], [2], remote sensing [3], [4], surveillance [5], video enhancement [6], and metaverse [7]. Traditional interpolation-based and model-based methods often struggle to recover fine details and high-frequency textures, limiting their practical utility [8], [9]. The advent of deep learning has transformed SISR, enabling models to learn complex mappings from LR to HR images directly from data. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [10] laid the foundation for modern SISR, offering superior reconstruction accuracy and end-to-end learning capabilities. Building on CNNs, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [11] introduced perceptually realistic image generation, while transformer-based architectures [12] have demonstrated exceptional ability in modeling long-range dependencies and global contextual information. More recently, diffusion-based approaches [13] have emerged, providing probabilistic frameworks for high fidelity image reconstruction. This survey provides a comprehensive review of these deep learning paradigms for SISR. It systematically categorizes existing methods into CNN based, GAN-based, transformer-based, and diffusion-based approaches, analyzing their architectural designs and their strengths and limitations. In addition, the survey discusses current challenges, while highlighting potential directions for future research. By presenting a unified perspective, this work aims to guide researchers and practitioners in understanding the state-of-the-art developments and emerging trends in deep learning-based SISR.

II. CLASSIFICATION

In SISR, LR images are typically generated by degrading their corresponding ground truth (GT) counterparts. The degradation model often involves downsampling operations (e.g., nearest-neighbor, bicubic, bilinear), blur kernels (e.g., disc, motion), and various noise types (e.g., Gaussian, impulse, camera, compression). The objective of an SISR model, as illustrated in Figure 1, is to learn an approximate inverse of this degradation process, thereby reconstructing the HR image from its LR input.

Figure 1. Framework of SISR

Deep learning-based SISR methods can be broadly classified according to their underlying technologies, including CNNs, GANs, transformers, and diffusion models. The classification is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Classification of Deep Learning-based SISR Models

2.1 CNN-based Models

As shown in Figure 3, for CNN-based SISR models, the process begins with patch extraction, where convolutional filters generate overlapping feature representations from the input LR image to capture local structures. These features then undergo non-linear mapping through successive convolutional layers with activation functions, enabling the network to learn complex LR-to-HR relationships. Finally, the reconstruction stage aggregates the transformed features and upsamples them to recover the high-resolution image with finer details and improved visual quality. The CNN-based models are categorized on the basis of their architectural designs as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 3. CNN Framework

a) Shallow Networks: Shallow CNN-based SISR models, such as SRCNN [14] and FSRCNN [15], were among the first to demonstrate the effectiveness of deep learning for super-resolution. SRCNN uses three-layer CNN architecture with feature extraction, non-linear mapping, and reconstruction layers, while FSRCNN improves speed

by introducing a de convolution layer for upscaling in the network instead of bicubic interpolation. These models are simple, easy to implement, and computationally efficient for small-scale images. Limited depth constrains their ability to capture complex textures and high-frequency details, often producing slightly blurred results.

b) Deep Residual Networks: These networks leverage very deep architectures with skip connections to facilitate gradient flow and stable training. VDSR [16] uses residual learning to predict the difference between LR and HR images. EDSR [17] further removes unnecessary modules like batch normalization and expands feature channels, while CARN [18] incorporates cascading residual blocks to improve multi scale feature learning. Although, these networks have improved reconstruction quality in terms of fine textures. However, they require high computational cost and memory requirements and are not be suitable for low-resource environments.

c) Residual-Dense Networks: Residual-dense networks utilize dense connections to allow each layer to access features from all preceding layers. RDN [19] combines residual and dense connections to improve information flow and feature reuse, while SRDenseNet [20] applies similar dense connectivity with local residual learning. These networks achieve rich feature representation, better preservation of fine details, and improved gradient propagation. However, the face increased number of parameters and complexity, leading to slower inference compared to shallower networks

d) Recursive Networks: Recursive networks apply the same set of convolutional layers repeatedly, enabling very deep architectures with parameter sharing. DRCN [21] uses recursive layers to extract features at multiple depths, DRRN [22] combines residual learning with recursion, and MemNet [23] incorporates memory blocks to retain long-term dependencies. These models achieves competitive performance with relatively fewer parameters due to weight sharing but are complex and unstable due to deep recursion, and inference is slower than standard feed-forward networks.

e) Attention-based Networks: Attention-based CNNs integrate mechanisms to focus on the most informative features. AFBNet [24] employs channel attention to adaptively rescale features, while GRFN [25] adds spatial attention to enhance both channel and spatial dependencies. The attention improves ability of the network to reconstruct high-frequency details and textures. However, may have higher computational cost, increased model size, and longer training times.

f) Lightweight Networks: Lightweight CNN architectures are designed for efficiency without significantly compromising performance. IMDN [26] uses information multi distillation modules to selectively retain informative features, IDN [27] employs iterative deep networks for compact inference, and PFFN [28] performs feature extraction using pyramid feature fusion network for efficient up scaling. These models enable fast inference, low memory footprint, and are suitable for real-time applications. But, they slightly compromise reconstruction quality compared to deep models, particularly for very large scaling factors.

2.2 GAN-based Models

As shown in Figure 4, GAN-based SISR frameworks [29] employ a generator to map LR images to their HR counterparts and a discriminator distinguishes reconstructed images from real ones. The generator is trained not only to minimize re construction errors but also to fool the discriminator, ensuring perceptual quality and realism. Through adversarial learning, the model produces HR outputs that are sharper and more photo-realistic compared to conventional CNN approaches. The GAN-based SISR networks can be categorized as:

Figure 4. GAN Framework

a) ResNet Generators:: SRGAN [30] introduced generative adversarial networks for SISR, employing a ResNet-based generator composed of residual blocks to model the mapping from LR to HR images. This models improved perceptual quality compared to traditional CNNs but produces artifacts and its train is unstable.

b) Residual-in-Residual Dense Blocks RRDB Generators:: ESRGAN [31] enhances SRGAN by introducing RRDBs, which combine dense and residual connections without batch normalization, enabling deeper networks with better feature extraction. PGAN [32] alleviates structural distortions, while simultaneously generating perceptually-pleasant details. These architectures improve gradient flow and reconstruct finer textures but have larger model size and thus increased computational complexity.

c) Attention-based Generators:: Attention-based GAN generators incorporate channel and spatial attention mechanisms to selectively emphasize important features. Models like MASRGAN [33] and HAN [34] adaptively focus on informative regions, enhancing both global structure and fine details. Although these networks improved reconstruction of textures and high-frequency structures but have more challenging training dynamics due to additional attention modules.

d) Lightweight GANs:: Lightweight GAN variants are designed for real-time or resource-constrained environments. SR-BigGAN [35] and SRARDA [36] reduce the number of parameters using compact architectures, depth-wise separable convolutions, and efficient residual blocks. These models provide fast inference and low memory footprint but at the cost of slightly reduced perceptual quality.

e) Discriminators:: Discriminators in GAN-based SISR guide the generator by distinguishing between real and generated images. DPSRGAN [37] evaluates image patches in dependently to enforce local realism, while V-SRGAN [38] uses relativistic discriminators to consider relative authenticity between real and fake images. These discriminators help in stabilizing training, mitigate mode collapse, and improve gradient feedback.

2.3 Transformer-based Models

As shown in Figure 5, transformer-based SISR models leverage self-attention mechanisms to capture long-range dependencies and global contextual information, overcoming the locality limitations of CNNs. By processing image patches as tokens, the model effectively learns inter-patch relationships, enabling robust feature representation. The final reconstruction stage integrates these globally-aware features to generate high resolution images with enhanced texture and structural fidelity.

Figure5. Transformer Framework

a) **Basic ViT Network::** Basic Vision Transformer (ViT) based SISR models, divide the input image into non overlapping patches and process them as sequential tokens, enabling global context modeling from the early layers [39], [40]. These models have the enhanced capability for capturing global relationships which lead to more consistent texture and structural reconstruction. Still, these networks have limitation in computationally complexity due to quadratic attention with respect to image size and high memory consumption which restricts practical deployment on large images or resource constrained devices

b) **Window Attention Models::** Window-based attention models, including SwinFR [41] and SwinDFN [42], divide the image into local windows and perform self-attention within each window. Shifted window strategies allow cross-window interactions while reducing computational cost compared to global attention. These networks provide efficient modeling of both local and semi-global features, significantly lower memory and computation compared to pure ViTs, while maintaining high reconstruction quality.

c) **Hierarchical Models::** Hierarchical Transformer architectures, such as Restormer [43] and HiT-SR [44], incorporate multi-level feature extraction and fusion using encoder decoder structures. These models process features at multiple scales, combining local and global context through hierarchical attention mechanisms. These networks have superior ability to capture multi-scale features and fine-grained details which come at the cost of higher computational complexity compared to window-based transformers and requires careful design to balance efficiency and reconstruction performance.

d) **Lightweight Networks:** Lightweight Transformer models, including Srconvnet [45], ACT [46] and CRAFT [47], focus on reducing model parameters and computational cost while retaining the benefits of self-attention. Techniques include linear attention, feature down-sampling, and efficient multi-head attention mechanisms. Although these networks provide fast inference and are suitable for mobile or embedded devices, while maintaining competitive SR performance. However, they compromise in reconstruction fidelity compared to full-scale transformer models

2.4 Diffusion-based Models

As shown in Figure 6, diffusion-based SISR approaches treat super-resolution as a generative denoising process, where an LR image is progressively refined into an HR output. The model begins with a noisy or degraded initialization and iteratively applies a reverse diffusion process, guided by the LR input, to recover fine-grained details. This probabilistic sampling framework enables the generation of diverse yet faithful HR reconstructions with improved stability and realism. The diffusion-based models are categorized as:

Figure 6. Diffusion Framework

a) **Conditional Diffusion Models:** Conditional diffusion models, such as DiffOSR [48], ResQu [49], and SRDiff [50], apply de-noising diffusion probabilistic frameworks to generate high-resolution images conditioned on low-resolution inputs. These models iteratively refine a noisy image over multiple time steps to reconstruct the target HR image. Such models are capable of producing highly realistic and diverse outputs with strong perceptual quality but are computationally expensive due to the need for thousands of de-noising steps.

b) **Latent Diffusion Models:** Latent diffusion approaches, such as SatDiffMoE [51], MoESR [52], and LDM [53], perform the diffusion process in a compressed latent space rather than the full image space. This reduces memory usage and accelerates sampling while maintaining reconstruction quality. These are significantly more efficient networks than pixel-space diffusion which retains perceptual quality while reducing computational requirements. However, quality may be slightly degraded compared to full-resolution diffusion models.

2.5 Hybrid Models

Hybrid SISR models integrate the strengths of different deep learning paradigms, such as CNNs, Transformers, GANs, or diffusion models, to achieve a better balance between fidelity, perceptual quality, and efficiency. For instance, SwinIR [54] combines CNN-based convolutional layers with Swin Transformer blocks to exploit both local feature extraction and global dependency modeling. TTSR (Texture Transformer SR) [55] fuses CNNs with Transformer attention to transfer realistic textures for enhanced perceptual quality. On the generative side, FSRDiff [56] and related frameworks combine diffusion sampling with adversarial training to achieve photo-realistic outputs with improved stability. Transformer Diffusion models integrate self-attention mechanisms into the diffusion framework to capture long-range dependencies and global context. Models like DiT-SR [57] and DWTrans [58] SR combine hierarchical or window-based attention with iterative denoising for enhanced SR reconstruction. These hybrid models address the limitations of single-architecture designs—such as the locality constraint of CNNs, the high complexity of Transformers, and instability in GANs by leveraging their complementary strengths, making them highly promising for robust and real-world SISR applications.

III. EVALUATION METRICS

The evaluation of SISR is carried out under standardized metrics to ensure fair comparison, which are formulated below.

A. Distortion-oriented Metrics

- Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR): PSNR [59] is the most commonly used metric to measure pixel-level fidelity. It is formulated as:

$$\text{PSNR} = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{MAX}_I^2}{\text{MSE}} \right)$$

Where, MAX_I is the maximum possible pixel value (255 for 8-bit images) and MSE is the mean squared error between the ground truth HR image I_{HR} and the reconstructed image I_{SR} .

- Structural Similarity Index (SSIM): SSIM [60] evaluates structural similarity between IHR and ISR, considering luminance (l), contrast (c), and structure (s) comparisons:

$$\text{SSIM}(x, y) = [l(x, y)]^\alpha \cdot [c(x, y)]^\beta \cdot [s(x, y)]^\gamma$$

Where, α, β, γ are weighting factors. SSIM values range between 0 and 1, with higher values indicating better structural preservation.

B. Distortion-oriented Metrics

Pixel-level metrics like PSNR and SSIM often fail to capture visual quality. Perceptual measures such as LPIPS [61] and NIQE [62] are used to evaluate realism. LPIPS compares deep feature representations between I_{SR} and I_{HR} , while NIQE assesses naturalness without reference images. High PSNR/SSIM indicates reconstruction accuracy, whereas low LPIPS/NIQE reflects better perceptual quality. SISR evaluations typically report both types of metrics to balance fidelity and perceptual realism.

IV. CHALLENGES WITH POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

SISR faces multiple challenges which are listed below with potential solutions as:

- Ill-posed nature: The solution space can be constrained by utilizing prior information such as self-similarity or multi-feature priors.
- Artifacts and Distortions: The real details can be distinguished from artifacts by using gradient-based losses or wavelet-domain losses.
- Limitations in Feature Extraction: The fine-detail recovery can be enhanced by designing hybrid architectures, attention mechanisms, and edge-preserving modules.
- Computationally Intensive: The computational complexity can be reduced by employing parameter sharing and pruning.
- Real-world degradations: The realistic degradations can be handled by developing blind SR methods and adaptive multi-feature prior approaches.

V. CONCLUSION

This survey presented a comprehensive review of deep learning-based SISR methods, categorizing them into CNN based, GAN-based, transformer-based, and diffusion-based paradigms. For each category, we analyzed architectural designs, algorithmic strategies, strengths, limitations, and applications. Despite notable progress, challenges remain, including the ill-posed nature of SISR, artifact generation, limited feature extraction, computational complexity, and real-world degradation handling. Future research can focus on lightweight, real time, and degradation-aware models to improve the performance.

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